

Differential Pulse Polarography and Adsorptive Stripping Voltammetric Determination of Uric Acid

MAHMOUD A. GANDOUR^a, ENSAF-ABOUL-KASIM^{*b}, A. H. AMRALLAH^b and O. A. FARGHALY^b

^aChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut, Egypt

^bChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Aswan, Egypt

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The complex formation between uric acid and zinc, cadmium and lead ions has been investigated using differential pulse polarography in 0.01 M NaNO₃. The complexes formed by Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} with uric acid have the stoichiometry of 1 : 2. Zn^{II} does not give any indication of complexation with uric acid.

A sensitive voltammetric method is developed for the quantitative determination of uric acid based on controlled adsorptive preconcentration of uric acid on the hanging mercury drop electrode. The modes used are direct current stripping voltammetry and differential pulse stripping voltammetry. The adsorptive stripping response was evaluated with respect to preconcentration time and potential, concentration dependence and composition of supporting electrolyte.

The metal-uric acid complexes have been rarely studied¹, whereas the electrochemical detection of uric acid has been studied by cathodic stripping voltammetry^{2,3}. The present study reports the interaction of Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} ions with uric acid.

Results and Discussion

Differential pulse polarography of the metal-uric acid interaction at low concentrations : The complex

formation between uric acid and lead(II) and cadmium(II) ions was investigated using differential pulse polarography in 0.01 M sodium nitrate ($\mu=0.01$) at pH 7.00 \pm 0.05. The metal ion concentration was kept at 1.0×10^{-5} M to which different increments of uric acid were added (0.8–8.0) 10^{-4} M. On increasing uric acid concentration, the shift in peak potential was found to occur (Fig. 1 as representative and Table 1).

Fig. 1. (a) Differential pulse polarograms for 1×10^{-5} M Pb^{II} in presence of 0.01 M NaNO₃ and at different concentrations of uric acid: (a) Pb^{II} alone, (b) 0.8×10^{-4} , (c) 1.6×10^{-4} , (d) 3.2×10^{-4} , (e) 4.8×10^{-4} , (f) 6.4×10^{-4} and (g) 8×10^{-4} M. (b) Plot of E_p vs $\log [UC]$ for Pb^{II}-UC system.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF DIFFERENTIAL PULSE PEAK POTENTIAL OF THE PEAK CURRENT AS A FUNCTION OF URIC ACID FOR $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ Pb^{II} AND Cd^{II} URIC ACID SYSTEMS

[UC] $\times 10^{-4} M$	Pb ^{II}		Cd ^{II}	
	$-\Delta E_p$ mV	i_p nA	$-\Delta E_p$ mV	i_p nA
0.0	—	24	—	64
0.8	20	78	8	67
1.6	33	112	15	93
3.2	43	126	25	152
4.8	53	84	35	210
6.4	63	84	45	190
8.0	63	84	45	225

The linear relation between ΔE_p and $\log [UC]$ does not cover the concentration range of uric acid. At $6.4 \times 10^{-4} M$ of uric acid (UC) the surface coverage is attained during the drop-life (1 s). At higher concentration of uric acid, it is assumed that Pb^{II}-UC and Cd^{II}-UC complexes and uric acid are accumulated at the electrode surface. The current of simple metal ion (Pb and Cd) is lower than that observed in the presence of the ligand. On adding uric acid, enhancement in the current was noticed indicating the adsorption of lead and cadmium complexes. The shift in peak potentials may therefore be due to complex formation and adsorption.

The half-peak width ($w^{1/2}$) values are 50–60 mV indicating that two electrons are consumed in the reduction process and the reaction is reversible (pulse amplitude = 25 mV), in close agreement with the calculated theoretical value⁴.

The basic relationship between potential shift and the ligand concentration can be expressed by the equation,

$$E_{1/2}^o - E_{1/2}^s = \frac{0.059}{n} \log K - \frac{0.059}{n} p \log (X)$$

The measured peak potential with differential pulse polarography is correlated to the ordinary half-wave potential (direct current polarography) by the equation,

$$E_p = E_{1/2} - \frac{\Delta E}{2}$$

where ΔE is the pulse amplitude. Hence, the shift in the peak potential in complex formation can be rewritten in the form,

$$E_p^o - E_p^s = \frac{0.059}{n} \log K_f - \frac{0.059}{n} p \log (X)$$

where E_p is the peak potential of the complexed ion in the presence of ligand with concentration X , E_p^o the peak potential in the absence of ligand (aquo-metal ion), n the number of electrons gained

in the reduction, K_f the apparent formation constant and p the complex coordination number.

The slopes of the straight lines obtained in plotting ΔE_p vs $\log [UC]$, are 0.055 and 0.049 for lead and cadmium respectively, and the corresponding coordination number being 1.63 and 1.8 which can be approximated to 2. This gives the stoichiometry of 1:2 metal-to-ligand ratio and the logarithmic values of the apparent stability constant are 9.47 and 11.7 for lead and cadmium respectively.

Effect of metal concentration: Differential pulse polarograms of Pb^{II}-UC and Cd^{II}-UC systems in the range of 5×10^{-6} to $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ of lead or cadmium ions and in a constant concentration of uric acid ($6.4 \times 10^{-4} M$) in 0.01 M sodium nitrate as supporting electrolyte, are presented graphically in Fig 2. A new less electronegative peak at concentration $\geq 25 \times 10^{-6} M$ of lead ($-0.64 V$) and cadmium ($-0.615 V$) ions, is observed, and this may be attributed to the reduction of the aquo-metal ions (easily reduced) which is in equilibrium with metal-urate complex. On plotting the peak current versus concentration of metal ions, straight lines passing through the origin are obtained.

The complex formation between uric acid and Zn^{II} ion was also investigated by differential pulse polarography in presence of 0.01 M NaNO₃ as supporting electrolyte ($\mu=0.01$) and at different concentrations of uric acid. It is found that on increasing the concentration of UC, there is no shift in peak potential. The peak potential of Zn^{II} ions either in nitrate solution or nitrate-urate mixture, is at $-1.03 V$ (Ag/AgCl saturated). This indicates that Zn^{II} ion does not form complex with urate solution under the present conditions.

Linear sweep adsorptive stripping analysis of uric acid: The above results reveal that the metal(II)-uric acid systems exhibit adsorption behaviour at the mercury surface and uric acid displays surface-active characters too. Uric acid is not reducible at the mercury electrode and becomes reducible after prolonged exposure to air⁶. Zongpeng *et al.*³ reported that polarographic currents and cathodic stripping peaks of uric acid are due to the formation of slightly soluble compounds with mercury.

In the present work, the cathodic stripping analysis is reinvestigated in a trial to verify the optimal condition for uric acid analysis. The modes used are linear sweep (100 mVs^{-1}) and differential pulse stripping voltammetry (5 mV^{-1} , 25 mV pulse amplitude).

Adsorptive linear sweep stripping voltammetric determination of uric acid: The effect of the supporting electrolyte composition such as sodium nitrate, sodium perchlorate, potassium chloride, disodium hydrogen phosphate (pH=9.8), borax solution (pH=9.1) and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH=5.65), on the direct current adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry of $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ of

Fig. 2. DP polarograms for $6.4 \times 10^{-4} M$ UC, in presence of $0.01 M$ NaNO_3 and at different concentrations of Pb^{II} ion : (a) 5×10^{-6} , (b) 1×10^{-5} , (c) 2×10^{-5} , (d) 3×10^{-5} , (e) 4×10^{-5} , (f) 5×10^{-5} , (g) 6×10^{-5} , (h) 7×10^{-5} , (i) 8×10^{-5} , (j) 9×10^{-5} and (k) $1 \times 10^{-4} M$.

UC at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.01$) was studied. Preliminary investigation showed that the preconcentration potential had a drastic changes on the voltammograms. Some experiments were done in KCl , NaNO_3 and Na_2HPO_4 . It has been concluded that the preconcentration potential should be held at $+0.25$ V against Ag/AgCl electrode ; more positive potentials may give a large peak due to the oxidation of mercury itself and the interferences from chloride and hydroxyl ions. Application of more negative potential may produce ill-defined peaks or no oxidation of uric acid occurs prior to the negative going scan.

In the case of borax, potassium chloride and disodium hydrogen phosphate solutions, large peaks in the same position of uric acid peak were observed due to their interferences. Therefore, these media are not recommended in the analysis of uric acid by cathodic stripping voltammetry. However, it has been shown from our experiments that these peaks were produced even in the absence of the analyte. This may be due to the interferences of OH^- ions.

However, Zonpeng *et al.*³ reported that alkaline borax and Britton-Robinson buffer can be used. The erroneous conclusion may come from the fact that the supporting electrolytes should be tested alone (i.e. without the addition of the analyte) by cathodic stripping voltammetry under the same set

of conditions to clarify the interferences that may be inherent with the analysis.

In the presence of NaNO_3 and NaClO_4 ($\text{pH}=6.4$), a well-defined but small peak was observed with a small increase in height as preconcentration time increases as shown in Fig. 3. Also, more sensitive peak ($+0.05$ V) was observed for $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid in $0.01 M$ acetic acid-acetate buffer using different preconcentration times and at different pHs (6.75, 5.65, 4.9 and 3.76), recorded using DC stripping. The plot of the peak current versus pH shows a decrease in current on increasing pH of the solution and the current attains a constant value at pHs 5.65 and 6.75. Above this range of pH, the OH^- ion obscures the reduction peak of the oxidised form of uric acid.

The effect of ionic strength ($1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ UC) was studied using different ionic strengths, viz. 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 and $0.07 M$ sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer ($\text{pH}=5.65$). A single peak was observed in each case. The enhancement of the peak current largely decreased by increasing the ionic strength. The plots of current versus preconcentration time (Fig. 4) give straight lines with slopes equal to 3.7, 3.0, 2.3 and 1.7 nA s^{-1} for 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 and $0.07 M$ respectively. This indicates that the best ionic strength is $0.01 M$ sodium acetate-acetic acid ($\text{pH}=5.65$).

Fig. 3. (a) DC stripping voltammograms for $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid in presence of $0.01 M$ NaNO_3 (scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} ; equilibrium time = 15 s): (a) residual, (b) 0.0 , (c) 30 , (d) 60 , (e) 90 , (f) 120 , (g) 150 and (h) 180 s . (b) DC stripping voltammograms for $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid in presence of $0.01 M$ NaClO_4 (scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} ; equilibrium time = 15 s): (a) residual, (b) 0.00 , (c) 30 , (d) 60 and (e) 90 s .

Fig. 4. Plots of i_p vs preconcentration time for $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid at different ionic strength and at constant $\text{pH} = 5.65$.

The effect of potential scan rate (v) on both current and potential of the peak of $8 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid was evaluated for the adsorbed UC. Plots of $\log i_p$ versus $\log v$ are linear over the $10\text{--}200 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ range with a slope of 0.88 which is in close proximity to a slope of 1.0 that is expected for ideal reaction of surface species⁷. A 20 mV negative shift in the peak potential was observed upon increasing the scan rate in the range given. The plot of E_p vs $\log v$ is also linear ($r = 0.98$).

Fig. 5 shows the peak current versus preconcentration time plots. The slopes of linear section are 3.6 and 5.9 nA s^{-1} for $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ and 9.5 nA s^{-1} for $8 \times 10^{-7} M$ UC with intersects at current axis and breaks at certain preconcentration times. The intercepts are due to the fact that adsorption occurs at the rest period (equilibrium time) which was fixed at 15 s . The breaks at certain stirring times means that the surface coverage is attained.

To reveal the adsorption of the analyte without convection (stirring), some experiments were carried out with $8 \times 10^{-7} M$ UC in quiescent solution. The observed linear dependence of the peak current on the square-root of the preconcentration time for a quiescent solution, is in a good agreement with the prediction of Delahay and Fike⁸ for the case of semi-infinite linear diffusion.

With $2.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ UC solution, full surface coverage was achieved after 30 s of stirring. Under

Fig. 5. (a) Plot of i_p vs pre-concentration time for $1.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid. (b) Plot of i_p vs pre-concentration time for $8 \times 10^{-7} M$ uric acid.

these conditions, the charge transferred in the reduction step corresponds to $1.86 \times 10^{-6} C$ as calculated by integration of the peak. A monolayer surface coverage of $6.006 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol cm}^{-2}$ can be estimated by division of the charge by nFA ($n=2$ electrons, $F=96500 \text{ C}$ and $A=0.016 \text{ cm}^2$). Consequently, each adsorbed uric acid occupies area of 0.276 nm^2 .

Adsorptive differential pulse stripping voltammetric determination of uric acid: Adsorptive stripping of uric acid can also be performed by changing the working mode. Differential pulse voltammetry is more sensitive than the linear sweep mode though it takes longer time due to the slow rate of scanning. The differential pulse stripping voltammetry of $8 \times 10^{-9} M$ UC was carried out in acetate buffer (pH=5.65) at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.01$). The accumulation of uric acid on the electrode surface may be given by studying the effect of pre-concentration time on the peak current (Fig. 6) in which the peak is observed with very small signal produced on plotting the peak current versus pre-concentration time, a straight line (Fig. 6) with

break at 90 s and intersect at 0.5 nA, indicating that adsorption at the first period (equilibrium time) is very weak and the surface coverage is attained in 90 s.

Using DPSV, a linear relation was observed in the range of 1.6×10^{-8} to $3.2 \times 10^{-7} M$ UC with break at $2.6 \times 10^{-7} M$ UC, indicating that the surface coverage is attained at this concentration.

Linear relations between peak current and pre-concentration time of $8 \times 10^{-9} M$ uric acid were observed, which indicates that this concentration may be considered as the lower limit of detection, i.e. 1.345 ppb using 25 mV pulse height.

Experimental

A PAR 264A polarographic analyser coupled with a RE 0089 x-y recorder was used. The working electrode was a PAR 303 static mercury drop electrode (medium size drop) equipped with a platinum auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl saturated KCl reference electrode.

Fig. 6. (a) Differential pulse stripping voltammograms for $8 \times 10^{-9} M$ uric acid in presence of $0.01 M$ acetate buffer (pH=5.65) (scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} ; equilibrium time 15 s): (a) residual, (b) 30, (c) 60, (d) 90, (e) 120, (f) 150, (g) 180 and (h) 210 s. (b) Plot of i_p vs. preconcentration time for $8 \times 10^{-9} M$ uric acid.

A stock solution of uric acid (B.D.H.) was prepared in double-distilled water and sodium hydroxide was added to facilitate the solubility process of uric acid. Supporting electrolytes (analytical grade) were prepared in double-distilled water. Stock solutions ($0.01 M$) of the metals were used. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Procedure: A known volume (10 ml) of the $0.01 M$ supporting electrolyte was added to the cell and deaerated by passing nitrogen for 12 min (and 30 s before stripping analysis). The scan rate was 100 mV s^{-1} for DCSV and 5 mV s^{-1} for DPSV. Pulse amplitude was 25 mV and pulse repetition 0.5 s.

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